

**THE USING OF REFLECTIVE MATERNAL METHOD
TO IMPROVE LANGUAGE LEARNING AND UNDERSTANDING
OF HEARING IMPAIRMENT STUDENTS IN GRADE 2
PEMALANG STATE EXTRAORDINARY SCHOOLS –
SLB NEGERI PEMALANG, INDONESIA**

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Abstract:

This research aims to test the effectiveness of using reflective maternal method in increasing interest in learning and understanding the language of hearing impairment students in grade 2 SLB Pemalang, with 6 numbered subjects, consisting of 3 boys and 3 girls. The researchers used a mixed method research (mixed methods research) sequential exploratory strategy type of design. The results showed an increase in interest in learning with the average percentage as follows 14.28%, 23.08%, 15.28%, 28.89%, 37.03% and 30.90%. The raising of students language understanding with an average increase as follows 15.62%, 26.18%, 14.28%, 26.18%, 25.79% and 35.59%.

Keywords: the using of maternal reflective method, interest in learning, language comprehension, learners with hearing impairment

1. Introduction

Hearing impairment learners in special schools is an integral part in obtaining a quality education, so the impacts of their hearing impairment can be minimized in order to be able to grow and socialize with other people. Basic education is the foundation to prepare students with hearing impairment to a higher level. Hearing impairment learners generally have problems in communicating that affect their learning and comprehension or understanding the language, which in return, affects their learning performance as well.

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In the educational process, both within the family and the community, but especially in schools, primary problem is the interest of students to learn. The factors of interests of learners with hearing impairment greatly affect the learning success. According Shadily (2000), the interest can be defined as a tendency to pay attention, and act against the people, activities, or situations that become the object of interest, accompanied by feelings of pleasure. So in the discussions contained a sense that there is a break in the interest of the subject's attention, there is an attempt to approach, know, possess, and control.

The second problem that significantly affects the success of learners with hearing impairment is the understanding of the language. The ability to understand language is very important for individual learners with hearing impairment because by the ability of understanding the language, learners with hearing impairment can communicate with others. But the reality of slow learners understand the language as a means of communication and information submitted by teachers in the learning process. Language is an important tool in communicating, studying science and in social life. Good learning process requires appropriate learning strategies, use of media or tools appropriate to the needs and characteristics of learners, so that the activities can be run more effectively, efficiently so that more successful with the maximum.

According to Airasian, et al (2010), the learner is said to understand when they can construct meaning from instructional messages, either orally, in writing, or graphics delivered through teaching, books, or computer screen. So we can say understanding is the result of learning, for example, students can explain by the composition of their own words on what they read or heard, to give another example of a teacher who had been exemplified. However, for learners with hearing impairment is very difficult to understand the language in the text (written) and understands the language of communication (verbal) with others. Here, the role of teachers and parents, which are required to communicate more creative in learning as well in the classroom as outside of the classroom.

Cecilia and Bunawan (2006) said that as educators, knowledge is the background of the language and its development needs to be known, because it will color the learning activities in the classroom. Language is a communication tool that is used to connect each other. If a group of people have the same language, it can be reasoned with everything that happened both concrete and abstract. With the communication then humans can form life and his world. Communication in the process of social interaction is an integral part of society, which was built with the aim to support the concept of self, identity, fulfillment of personal needs, self-actualization, influence the

feelings, thoughts and behaviors of others, survival, building new ideas and solutions problem.

A child with hearing impairment is a child who experienced a lack or loss of hearing ability due to damage or malfunction in part or all of the hearing instrument so that it faces obstacles in language development. Children who have hearing loss are not able to listen as well. As a result, the deaf children do not undergo the process of imitation after the babble noise, the process of imitation is only limited visual mimicry alone. So, during the subsequent development of deaf children, there will be difficulties in language development and speech. This situation will result on problems for deaf children when dealing with normal people.

Deafness suffered since birth will lead to various issues concerning the whole life and the lives of disabling. The biggest problem experienced is someone that when a loss or reduction of hearing function is a bottleneck in communication with the environment.

Based on the limitations of learners with hearing impairment in learning and understanding language, it is required the right method for language learning on learners with hearing impairment. One method that can be used that method Maternal Reflective (MMR). This method emphasizes learning model mother to child. Mother has always an active role in providing stimulus to the child. Mother's active role consist on giving stimulus to the child and establishing direct communication in the form of questions that lead to daily activities experienced by children.

According Sunarto (2005), Methods Maternal Reflective is a lesson that follows how a child hears to master the native language, the starting point on the language and communication needs of children and not in the program language rules that need to be taught or presents language as natural as possible to the children both expressive and reflective, demanding that all the problems of children who reflective discussion. The application of Maternal Reflective Method requires teachers to act like mothers to the students. The learning activities are focused on the experience of learners with hearing impairment that day or the previous day. Deaf learners are expected to submit or re-tell the experience that he experienced. It is to arouse the interest of learners with hearing impairment. It aims to stimulate interest in learning, stimulate the child's ability to deliver something that is associated with the development of communication and language learners with hearing impairment.

Maternal Reflective Method is part of a strategy that is meant to develop the quality of learners to fit the demands of the curriculum that are listed in the national education system, as well as reflections in improving the performance of educators.

This method also refers to the application of informal education conducted in the school environment. It could be said that this method is a merger between formal and informal education. No doubt that the conversation is the main characteristic of the schools using methods maternal reflective.

Conversations will color all learning activities throughout the day. The conversation will be the shaft, a motor, and trigger speed language development process in particular, and all other fields of science. Conversation, deaf learners to communicate in accordance with the age and language skills that will arouse the interest of learners with hearing impairment to know what were spoken. By knowing the contents of the conversation, learners with hearing impairment are able to understanding the language in conversations (spoken language).

This research aimed to test the effectiveness of Maternal Reflective Methods to improve their learning and understanding of the language for deaf children in special schools.

2. Research Methods

The research method that the writer use is a mixed method research (mixed methods research) type of Exploratory Sequential Design (sequential exploratory strategy paper) (Creswell & Clark, 2007; Creswell, 2012) modified as needed. The design of this research strategy combines qualitative with quantitative research. The collection and analysis of qualitative data was conducted in the first phase, followed by the collection and analysis of quantitative data in the second phase which is based on the results of the first stage. Modifications done by giving priority which more likely in the second stage, and the process of mixing (mixing) is done when researchers linked the data analysis of qualitative and quantitative data collection. Research carried out by the research subject is class of grade 2 in SLB Pematang as many as six children, three boys and three girls. These classes have been the subject of study because their students have a low interest in learning and understanding the language.

3. Results

a. Qualitative Research

Preliminary observations in grade 2 SLB Pematang, language learning with Maternal Reflective Method has not run optimally, because that the learning and understanding of language learners in language learning is still low. This resulted in the acquisition

value of 6 learners Grade 2 with minimal completeness criteria predetermined value is 65, only two students who have finished with a score of 70 and 75 were obtained from the report cards documentation.

The foregoing is not maximized because learners in completing the task given teacher, interest in learning less and slow to understand the information provided by the teacher is not maximized in exploiting and using the media, lack of exercise so that when testing the students are not able to do well.

b. Quantitative Research

1. Interest to Learn

Apri (2014) expressed interest in learning is a concern, a sense of love, a person's interest (students) to study activity demonstrated through enthusiasm, participation and activeness in learning and realize the importance of that activity. Assessment is done through observation before (Pre-) and after (post-) the use of maternal reflective method. Assessment of pre-action made at the time teachers do not use methods maternal reflective. Assessment of post-action carried out at the time of using maternal reflective teacher. Recapitulation average scores assessment results interests of learners presented in Table 1, while the ratio of the average score pre- and post- treatment are presented in Figure 1.

Subject Name	The Average Score Ratings		The Rate of Change	
	Pre-action	Post-action	Score	Percentage
A	2,8	3,2	0,4	14,28%
B	2,8	3,64	0,84	23,08%
C	2,7	3,2	0,5	15,62%
D	2,7	3,48	0,78	28,89%
E	2,7	3,7	1,0	37,03%
F	2,2	2,88	0,68	30,90%

Table 1: Summary of average assessment learning interest pre-action and post-action methods maternal reflective

Figure 2: Comparison of interest in learning assessment score pre-action and post-action by using maternal reflective methods

2. Language Understanding

Winkel and Mukhtar (Sudaryono, 2012), understanding is the ability to grasp the meaning and significance of the material being studied, expressed by outlining the basic contents of a reading or changing data presented in some form to another form. Assessment is the same as the interest in learning, assessment is carried out in the pre-action and post-action to the use of maternal reflective. Recapitulation average scores assessment results interests of learners presented in Table 2, while the ratio of the average score pre- and post- treatment are presented in Figure 2.

Subject Name	The Average Score Ratings		The Rate of Change	
	Pre-action	Post-action	Score	Percentage
A	3,2	3,7	0,5	15,62%
B	3,17	4,0	0,83	26,18%
C	3,2	3,6	0,4	14,28%
D	3,04	3,7	0,66	26,18%
E	3,18	4,0	0,82	25,79%
F	2,95	4,0	1,05	35,59%

Table 1: Summary of average assessment language understanding pre-action and post-action maternal reflective methods

Figure 2: Comparison of language comprehension assessment scores pre and post actions using maternal reflective methods

4. Discussion

Deafness hampered the ability of proficiency. Deafness also leads to understanding of the language and interest in learning to be low. This is due to habituation of children who use sign language on the development of language skills. The use of Maternal Reflective Method to train deaf to improve their language skills. Jatun (2007) Maternal Reflective Method is learning model to improve language skills, which in turn will enhance the ability to communicate.

Factors underlying the use of maternal reflective method, according Bintoro, (2008), factors of maternal reflective methods include: 1) Verbal: (a) oral / verbal, (b) writing, (c) to read the speech. 2) Non-verbal: (a) gesture, (b) expression, (c) cues: cue raw, natural gesture. Maternal reflective method of deaf children are taught to always use oral language, which is done with the conversation anywhere, anytime. Language training which takes place regularly and can be used as an effort in the development of language education for deaf children that language comprehension abilities and skills improve, so that the growing interest in learning the deaf.

Interest in learning for deaf children can be improved by using the method of maternal reflective to the average percentage increase for learners with hearing impairment as follows: 14.28%, 23.08%, 15.28%, 28.89%, 37.03% and 30.90%. Interest in learning can be assessed from the interaction of children with hearing impairment and interest in the subject. According Shadily (2000) the interest can be defined as a tendency to pay attention, and act against the people, activities, or situations that become the object of interest, accompanied by feelings of pleasure.

Sense of excitement in learning will foster greater understanding in children with hearing impairment, especially in language comprehension. Winkel and Mukhtar

(Sudaryono, 2012), the understanding is the ability to grasp the meaning and significance of the material being studied, expressed by outlining the basic contents of a reading or changing data presented in some form to another form.

The ability of understanding the language of deaf children by using maternal reflective views of the research results can improve the understanding of language learners with hearing impairment to the percentage increase in average as follows: 15.62%, 26.18%, 14.28%, 26.18%, 25.79% and 35.59%.

The using of maternal reflective method based on a study showed an increase of pre- and post-action measures can improve their learning and understanding of the language through language proficiency training.

5. Conclusion

Based on research that has been done can be mentioned that the maternal reflective method can improve learning and understanding the language of hearing impairment students with a percentage increase interest in learning as follows: 14.28%, 23.08%, 15.28%, 37.03% and 30.90%. For language understanding experienced an average percentage increase as follows: 15.62%, 26.18%, 14.28%, 26.18%, 25.79% and 35.59%. This case illustrates that the using of prioritizing reflective maternal oral or speech intelligibility is more effectively used in the classroom compared to the use of sign language.

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